

Temperature & Humidity Measurement

Monitoring the world around us since 1864

MUNRO

R W Munro Limited

Monitoring the World Around us Since 1864

The Founder Robert William Munro, F.R.Met.Soc. 1839-1912

Established in 1864, R W Munro has become synonymous with meteorological and hydrological equipment sales and service. Since production of the first Dines Pressure Tube Anemometer in 1892, R W Munro has achieved a reputation for excellence in providing instruments and systems of the highest quality to measure, monitor and record environmental phenomena. Today, Munro products extend right across the technological spectrum. Combining the traditional reliability of Munro craftsmanship with the benefits of the latest electronics enables Munro to supply standard and specialist equipment to meteorological offices, water authorities and government departments world-wide.

Temperature and Humidity

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Temperature and Humidity

Accurate measurement of temperature, forms an essential part of the observation routine at all synoptic stations. For, in conjunction with other observations from auxiliary, climatological, agricultural and health resort stations, information is provided for weather forecasts and to assist the needs of agriculture and industry.

At each scheduled hour, an observation is made of the dry-bulb and wet-bulb temperatures. These readings are then used to derive the vapour pressure, relative humidity and dew-point.

At certain specified hours, the extreme screen temperatures (maximum & minimum) are recorded, along with grass minimum and earth temperatures at various depths.

Comprehension of the ambient temperature and relative humidity, is an invaluable asset when control of the environment in the workplace is necessary - often you may find this to be a legal obligation. In order to ensure that comfortable working conditions are maintained, by ventilation, heating and refrigeration units, the temperature and humidity must be continuously monitored.

These factors are also of vital importance within storage facilities, computer rooms, agricultural buildings, archive and museums and diverse manufacturing processes. The development of plants and animals is equally affected by their micro-climate. Operation of electronic equipment and the preservation of books, documents, media and pictures would suffer, if the temperature and humidity of their environment were neglected.

This catalogue illustrates instruments and allied equipment, which are recommended for the measurement and recording of temperature and humidity, in all of these applications.

Screen Thermometers

Principles of Operation

Ordinary Thermometers

Normally used in pairs, as a wet-and-dry bulb hygrometer, the mercury filled ordinary thermometer is usually mounted vertically within a thermometer screen. The bulb of one has a muslin cover, kept wet by distilled water drawn from a reservoir. Ambient air temperature is provided by the dry-bulb, whilst relative humidity is calculated from the temperatures displayed by both thermometers.

Maximum & Minimum Thermometers

Usually mounted in a thermometer screen with a 5° incline to the horizontal, the mercury filled maximum and ethanol spirit filled minimum thermometer indicate the extremes of ambient air temperature experienced since the instrument was last reset. In operation, the minimum thermometer utilises a small black glass index, which is drawn along the bore by the contracting liquid. The index remains stationary at the extreme position, until the thermometer is reset. A constriction to the bore of the maximum thermometer, between the bulb and scale, enables the mercury to expand as the temperature increases but prevents the mercury receding as the temperature falls. The mercury column will remain at the extreme position until the thermometer is reset.

Sheathed Pattern Thermometers B843-844-849-850-855-856
Manufactured in accordance with the requirements of the British Meteorological Office and to British Standard 692. The thermometer stem, subdivided every 0.5°C for accuracy and figured at 5° intervals, is fused to the outer glass sheath to form a permanent seal, so that no condensation can occur. A rubber ring, placed between the stem and sheath, supports the far end of the stem.

SPECIFICATIONS

Sheathed Pattern Thermometers

Reference	range	accuracy	division	dimensions
B843	-10 to +65°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	330 x 14 mm
B844	-20 to +55°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	330 x 14 mm
B849	-25 to +50°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	330 x 14 mm
B850	-35 to +40°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	330 x 14 mm
B855	-20 to +55°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	330 x 14 mm
B856	-30 to +45°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	330 x 14 mm

Screen Thermometers

Mahogany Frame Pattern Thermometers

B845-846-851-852-877-878

Divided at 0.5° intervals, a solid stem thermometer is supported by a weather resistant laminated plastic scale plate. Indelibly marked every 5° and figured at 10° intervals, the scale plate and thermometer are mounted on a polished mahogany frame with sturdy brass guard, to protect the bulb from accidental damage. Fitted with two brass hanging-plates.

Plastic Scale Thermometers B847-848-853-854-857-858

Mounted on to a strong weather resistant laminated plastic scale, indelibly marked every 5° and figured at 10° intervals, a solid stem thermometer is clearly subdivided into 0.5° units. Two fixing holes are provided through the scale plate to enable the thermometer to be hung inside a thermometer screen.

SPECIFICATIONS

Mahogany Frame Pattern Thermometers

Reference	range	accuracy	division	dimensions
B845	-10 to +65°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	345 x 87 x 28 mm
B846	-20 to +55°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	345 x 87 x 28 mm
B851	-25 to +50°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	345 x 87 x 28 mm
B852	-35 to +40°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	345 x 87 x 28 mm
B877	-20 to +55°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	345 x 87 x 28 mm
B878	-30 to +45°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	345 x 87 x 28 mm

Plastic Scale Pattern Thermometers

Reference	range	accuracy	division	dimensions
B847	-10 to +65°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	330 x 48 x 12 mm
B848	-20 to +55°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	330 x 48 x 12 mm
B853	-25 to +50°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	330 x 48 x 12 mm
B854	-35 to +40°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	330 x 48 x 12 mm
B857	-20 to +55°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	330 x 48 x 12 mm
B858	-30 to +45°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	330 x 48 x 12 mm

R W Munro Ltd. reserve the right to alter specifications of equipment at any time, in the interests of improving quality and performance

Autographic Instruments

Principles of Operation

This range of instruments continuously records the air temperature and relative humidity of the local environment, on a scaled rectangular chart fitted round a rotating clock drum.

At full synoptic, agrometeorological, auxiliary and climatological stations, a thermograph and hygrograph are placed within a large thermometer screen, to produce records for meteorological work.

Throughout industry, these instruments are used to monitor manufacturing facilities, storage areas and computer rooms, so that the optimum environment is maintained.

Agricultural buildings, the horticultural industry and research laboratories are other important groups of users that incorporate these instruments, to monitor and control their micro-climate.

Thermograph B814

Supported on a sturdy cast alloy base, the hinged cover is perforated on the top and three sides to allow free airflow around the temperature sensitive element. The temperature element is a bimetallic coil, whose curvature changes are magnified and transmitted to the recording pen. Also mounted on the base, the mechanical clock will rotate the recording drum either daily (D) or weekly (W), depending on choice of clock. As standard this model is fitted with a disposable cartridge pen, black in colour, which will allow many months of recording before replacement is necessary. Alternatively, a fibre nib, wetted with black ink, is also available. A wide choice of operating ranges allows this instrument to be configured to suit most applications.

Hygrograph B815

Presented in a similar case to the thermograph, this instrument records the relative humidity of the air. Humidity readings, normally expressed as a percentage, are obtained from the alteration in length of a human-hair element, which is then magnified and transmitted to a recording pen. Mounted on the sturdy cast alloy base, the mechanical clock will rotate the recording drum either daily (D) or weekly (W), depending on choice of clock. A disposable cartridge pen, green in colour, is fitted as standard and will allow many months of recording before replacement is necessary. Alternatively a fibre nib, wetted with green ink, is also available.

SPECIFICATIONS

Thermographs

Reference	range	accuracy	weight	dimensions mm
B814/1	0 to +50°C	±0.5°C	2.5 kg	190 (H) x 260 (W) x 130 (D)
B814/2	0 to +60°C	±0.5°C	2.5 kg	190 (H) x 260 (W) x 130 (D)
B814/3	-10 to +40°C	±0.5°C	2.5 kg	190 (H) x 260 (W) x 130 (D)
B814/4	-20 to +40°C	±0.5°C	2.5 kg	190 (H) x 260 (W) x 130 (D)

Hygrographs

Reference	range	accuracy	weight	dimensions mm
B815	0 - 100% RH	±5% RH	2.5 kg	220 (H) x 260 (W) x 130 (D)

Suffix D for daily clock - W for weekly clock

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Autographic Instruments

Thermo-Hygrograph B801

This instrument combines the features of the thermograph and hair hygrograph, to record air temperature and relative humidity onto the same chart. The hinged cover is perforated on the top and three sides, to allow free airflow around the bimetallic temperature sensor. Mounted below the case, the human hair humidity element is protected by a perforated guard. Fitted to the sturdy cast alloy base, a mechanical clock rotates the clock drum either daily (D) or weekly (W), depending on the choice of clock. Disposable cartridge pens are fitted as standard - black for temperature, green for humidity - and will allow many months recording before replacement is necessary. Alternatively, fibre nibs wetted with black and green ink are also available. A wide choice of operating temperature scales allows this instrument to be configured to suit most applications.

Dual Height Thermo-Hygrograph B801A

Mounted onto a strong cast alloy base, the temperature sensor and humidity element are supported within a rigid lattice framework. The temperature sensor is a bimetallic coil, whose curvature changes are magnified then transmitted to the recording pen. Humidity readings, expressed as a percentage, are obtained from the alteration in length of the human hair element, which is again magnified and transmitted to the recording pen. Incorporated within this transmission mechanism are two cams, which convert the response of the human hair element into a linear movement over the full scale of the chart. The base also supports the pen lift assembly and the battery driven quartz clock. Selectable for either daily (D) or weekly (W) rotation, the clock drum accommodates the dual height chart. Disposable pen cartridges - black for temperature, green for humidity - are fitted as standard, to allow many months recording before replacement is necessary. The instrument is finished in stove enamel, with a perforated perspex cover with hinged carrying handle.

SPECIFICATIONS

Thermo-Hygrographs

Reference	range	accuracy	weight	dimensions mm
B801/1	0 to +50°C	±0.5°C/±5% RH	2.75 kg	220 (H) x 260 (W) x 130 (D)
B801/2	0 to +60°C	±0.5°C/±5% RH	2.75 kg	220 (H) x 260 (W) x 130 (D)
B801/3	-10 to +40°C	±0.5°C/±5% RH	2.75 kg	220 (H) x 260 (W) x 130 (D)
B801/4	-20 to +40°C	±0.5°C/±5% RH	2.75 kg	220 (H) x 260 (W) x 130 (D)
B801A/1	0 to +50°C	±0.5°C/±5% RH	4.0 kg	305 (H) x 280 (W) x 150 (D)
B801A/2	0 to +60°C	±0.5°C/±5% RH	4.0 kg	305 (H) x 280 (W) x 150 (D)
B801A/3	-10 to +40°C	±0.5°C/±5% RH	4.0 kg	305 (H) x 280 (W) x 150 (D)
B801A/4	-20 to +40°C	±0.5°C/±5% RH	4.0 kg	305 (H) x 280 (W) x 150 (D)

All Thermo-Hygrographs have a range of 0 to 100% RH

Suffix D for daily clock - W for weekly clock

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Thermometer Screens

Principles of Operation

To allow a true comparison between temperatures taken within the same site, or at differing geographical locations, the thermometers must be exposed in as near standard conditions as possible. Accordingly, those thermometers employed to determine the air temperature, the extremes of air temperature and the humidity are located in a thermometer screen of an approved design. The screen is designed to protect the thermometers from the effects of direct radiation and precipitation, whilst allowing the free movement of air through the screen. Finished in good quality white gloss paint, the screen is usually supported by means of a rigid iron stand, the base of which is set firmly in the ground. To comply with Meteorological Office requirements, the stand must elevate the screen, so that the bulbs of the vertically mounted wet and dry bulb thermometers are 1.25 metres above the ground.

Stevenson Screens B835

Manufactured to a British Meteorological Office design, this screen is constructed from seasoned timber, finished with three coats of top quality white gloss paint, to reflect radiation. The front, back and side panels are double-louvred with the outer layer sloping down and outward. The front panel has two brass hinges at the base to form a door. When open, this is retained in the horizontal position by two chains and can be padlocked when closed. The roof is double layered, with an air space between inner and outer components. The floor consists of three partially overlapping boards. Internal supports are arranged to accommodate either mahogany frame or plastic scale pattern thermometers as standard.

Self Assembly Screen B836

When constructed to the detailed and illustrated instructions, the fully machined component parts will assemble to form a screen identical to the ready-made version B835, with all screws, panel pins, hinges, chains and a hasp, being provided. The only additional materials required are glue, paint and a padlock.

Screen Stands B837

An iron stand, which can be set in the ground, forms a rigid support to elevate a screen to the recommended height. Finished in black enamel, stands are available to suit the Stevenson screen or large thermometer screen.

SPECIFICATIONS

Stevenson Screens

Reference	Int. dims. mm	Ext. dims. mm	Weight
B835	405 (H) x 445 (W) x 240 (D)	540 (H) x 580 (W) x 420 (D)	14 kg
B836	405 (H) x 445 (W) x 240 (D)	540 (H) x 580 (W) x 420 (D)	14 kg

Iron Stand

B837	1280 (H) x 480 (W) x 300 (D)	23 kg
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Thermometer Screens

Large Thermometer Screen B838

Designed to house two autographic instruments, thermograph and hair hygograph, as well as sheathed pattern thermometers, this screen is constructed from seasoned timber to a British Meteorological Office design. The four vertical panels are double-louvred and the floor consists of overlapping boards. The front panel has two bottom mounted brass hinges, to form a door. When open, this is retained in the horizontal position by two chains. A hasp and staple are provided to accommodate a padlock when the door is closed. The resin-bonded marine plywood roof, double layered with an air space between inner and outer components, provides excellent weatherproofing. The complete screen is further protected by three coats of top-quality white paint.

Screen Stands B839

An iron stand, which can be set in the ground, forms a rigid support to elevate a screen to the recommended height. Finished in black enamel, stands are available to suit the Stevenson screen or large thermometer screen.

SPECIFICATIONS

Stevenson Screens

Reference	Int. dims. mm	Ext. dims. mm	Weight
B838	420 (H) x 990 (W) x 292 (D)	585 (H) x 1220 (W) x 495 (D)	39 kg

Iron Stand

B839		1380 (H) x 1240 (W) x 510 (D)	36 kg
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Hygrometers

Kew Pattern Hygrometer B879-880

Manufactured to a British Meteorological Office design, this hygrometer is normally located within a thermometer screen, but is easily accommodated elsewhere, since it is provided with a substantial mounting board. Two mercury filled thermometers, with their stems subdivided every 0.5° and figured at 5° intervals, are mounted onto laminated plastic scale plates. In turn, these scale plates are fitted to a marine plywood back board. Water drawn up from a glass reservoir by a cotton wick, provides moisture to a circle of muslin surrounding one thermometer bulb, to produce a wet-bulb reading. The remaining thermometer will indicate air temperature. Supported by a metal strap attached to the backboard, the water reservoir has a cover to prevent the ingress of contaminants.

Mason's Pattern Hygrometer B840A

Mounted within a protective copper case, two mercury filled thermometers are positioned over a printed scale plate, divided every 1° and scaled at 5° intervals, allowing calculation of relative humidity to an accuracy of 2%. A fabric sleeve, one end immersed in the water filled plastic reservoir, surrounds one thermometer to produce a wet-bulb reading. The remaining thermometer will indicate air temperature. Supplied with spare fabric sleeve and hygrometric tables for the computations of relative humidity.

Whirling Hygrometer B842

Manufactured in accordance with British Standard 2842, the mercury filled thermometers have a lens front to magnify the mercury column. Engraved along the stem, both thermometers are calibrated every 0.5° and figured at 5° intervals. The thermometers and polyethylene water reservoir are located within a strong alloy frame that is rotated around a sturdy fold-down handle. A fabric sleeve, immersed in the reservoir, surrounds one thermometer, to produce a wet-bulb reading. The remaining thermometer will indicate air temperature. Supplied with a lined carrying case and hygrometric tables.

SPECIFICATIONS

Kew Pattern Hygrometer

Reference	range	accuracy	weight	dimensions mm
B879	-20 to +55°C	± 2% RH	800 g	380 (H) x 140 (W) x 50 (D)
B880	-30 to +45°C	± 2% RH	800 g	380 (H) x 140 (W) x 50 (D)

Masons Pattern Hygrometer

Reference	range	accuracy	weight	dimensions mm
B840A	-5 to +50°C	± 2% RH	250 g	290 (H) x 85 (W) x 35 (D)

Whirling Hygrometer

Reference	range	accuracy	weight	dimensions mm
B842	-5 to +50°C	± 2% RH	200 g	230 (H) x 145 (W) x 30 (D)

Earth Thermometers

Principles of Operation

Additional thermometers are required to be exposed outside the screen, usually on or near to the surface and at specified depths below the earth's surface. To enable the successful measurement of these temperatures, three different types of earth thermometer are offered, which between them, meet the requirements of meteorological departments, agriculture and industry in many countries. All three types of thermometer indicate the earth's temperature, by the expansion of a mercury column and have a similar accuracy.

Right angled Pattern B864-867

Manufactured to the requirements of the British Meteorological Office, to measure earth temperatures at depths up to 300 mm, a solid mercury-in-glass thermometer is formed so that the bulb is at right angles to the scale. The vertical limb, containing the bulb, is immersed to the required depth and left permanently in position. The scale, presented on the horizontal limb, is subdivided every 0.5° and figured at 5° intervals and lies along the surface.

SPECIFICATIONS

Right Angled Pattern Thermometer

Reference	range	accuracy	division	immersion
B864	-7 to +38°C	±0.2°C	0.5°C	50 mm
B865	-7 to +38°C	±0.2°C	0.5°C	100 mm
B866	-7 to +38°C	±0.2°C	0.5°C	200 mm
B867	-7 to +38°C	±0.2°C	0.5°C	300 mm

Earth Thermometers

Symons Pattern B859

Manufactured to the requirements of the British Meteorological Office, a solid stem mercury filled thermometer is suspended within a transparent sheath made of stout glass tubing. Subdivided every 0.5° for accuracy and figured at 5° intervals, the scale is easily read through the outer glass sheath. The bulb of the thermometer is embedded in a micro-crystalline wax, so it will not be affected by changes in temperature when drawn to the surface to take a reading. Two rubber rings round the sheath, protect the glass during insertion and withdrawal. In conjunction with an earth tube, this thermometer can be used to measure earth temperatures at depths of 300mm, or more.

Earth Tubes B860 - B863

A seamless steel tube, black stove enamelled for protection, incorporates a brass pointed end for ease of sinking. A removable flange, set 150mm from the top end, controls the exact immersion depth and prevents the entry of standing water. A brass cap seals the tube and provides an anchorage for the chain, from which the thermometer hangs. Permanently set in the earth, tubes are available for depths from 300mm up to 3m.

SPECIFICATIONS

Symons Pattern Thermometer

Reference	range	accuracy	division	dimensions
B859	-10 to +45°C	±0.2°C	0.5°C	360 x 20 mm

Earth Tubes for Symons Pattern

Reference	immersion
B860	300 mm
B861	500 mm
B862	1 metre
B863	3 metres

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Earth Thermometers

Enclosed Scale Pattern B868-874

Meteorological departments and Agrometeorological stations in many countries employ this pattern to measure earth temperatures at various depths, from the surface down to 1200 mm. A mercury-in-glass type thermometer is mounted onto an opal scale. When supported by a thermometer bracket, the lower portion of the thermometer is placed vertically in the earth, with the bulb at the required immersion depth. The scale, indelibly marked every 0.2° for accuracy, is presented at a 60° angle, so a reading is easily taken in situ without disturbing the thermometer. Insulated by an outer glass sheath, to which they are fused, the glass stem and scale are unaffected by the atmosphere and upper levels of earth.

Brackets B875

Constructed from steel with black stove-enamelled finish, the support bracket B875 is set permanently in the earth to support the insulated pattern thermometer at the required immersion depth. Two clips restrain the thermometer whilst, leaving the scale in clear view.

SPECIFICATIONS

Enclosed Scale Pattern

Reference	range	accuracy	division	immersion
B868	-10 to +55°C	±0.2°C	0.2°C	surface
B869	-10 to +55°C	±0.2°C	0.2°C	50 mm
B870	-10 to +55°C	±0.2°C	0.2°C	100 mm
B871	-10 to +55°C	±0.2°C	0.2°C	200 mm
B872	-10 to +55°C	±0.2°C	0.2°C	300 mm
B873	-10 to +55°C	±0.2°C	0.2°C	600 mm
B874	-10 to +55°C	±0.2°C	0.2°C	1220 mm

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